

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATIONS ON AEROELASTIC STABILITY OF COMBINED PLUNGE-PITCH MODE SHAPES IN A LINEAR COMPRESSOR CASCADE

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ABSTRACT

The effect of mode shape and reduced frequency on the flutter stability of a linear low-speed compressor cascade was investigated experimentally, employing the aerodynamic influence coefficient (AIC) approach. This paper describes in detail the methodology, experimental setup, and measurement techniques, presents experimentally determined influence coefficients, and discusses the findings with regards to the aeroelastic design parameter “plunge-to-twist incidence ratio”.

The influence of the vibrating blade on itself was always stabilizing, while other blades, mainly the first pressure side neighbour, vibrating at forward-travelling, low nodal diameter IPBAs, can destabilize the reference blade. As PTIR is increased, the phase of the complex modal force coefficients (AICs) of all blades is decreased, increasing the stabilizing effect of the vibrating blade on itself and overall cascade stability. Within the considered parameter range, the impact of reduced frequency is eliminated to a large extent if the incidence ratio is kept constant, requiring the torsion axis setback to be adjusted accordingly.

The findings show that the plunge-to-twist incidence ratio is a meaningful aeroelastic design parameter that can explain the global effect of mode shape on flutter stability and should be considered early in the aeromechanical blade design process to ensure flutter-free blading.

Keywords: Aeroelasticity, Flutter, Unsteady Aerodynamics, AIC-Method, Linear Compressor Cascade

NOMENCLATURE

b	Blade span
c	Blade chord
\tilde{c}_M	unsteady moment / modal force coefficient
c_p, \tilde{c}_p	Steady and unsteady coefficient of pressure
h, h_{LE}, h_{TE}	Plunge, leading and trailing edge displacement
k	Reduced frequency

M_{TA}	Aerodynamic moment about torsion axis
q	Dynamic pressure
U_0	Free-stream velocity
W_{aero}	Aerodynamic work per vibration cycle
x_F, z_F	Torsion axis setback from LE, mid-chord
α_0	Angle of attack (un-deflected blade)
β	Inlet flow angle
γ_0	Stagger angle (un-deflected blade)
θ_p, θ_t	Plunge and twist incidence (quasi-steady)
ϑ	Twist/modal displacement angle
$\sigma, IBPA$	Inter-blade phase angle
$\Phi_\theta, PTIR$	Plunge-to-twist incidence ratio

1. INTRODUCTION

Modern aero-engine compressor designs strive for reduced weight and maximum efficiency. Thinner, lighter blades have reduced stiffness, and with blade-integrated disks (BLISK), structural damping is almost completely eliminated, making such designs susceptible to aeroelastic phenomena like flutter. Among various aeroelastic and aerodynamic parameters, the mode shape is known to have a very large, if not the largest influence on the flutter stability of a blade row [1–3]. The fundamental bending or “flap” (1F) mode shape of modern compressor blades typically contains both a bending* and a torsion† component, which vibrate in-phase and with a fixed amplitude ratio that is determined solely by the structural properties of the blade.

Such combined mode shapes have been studied numerically, and it has been demonstrated that flutter stability is increased by reducing the torsional component of the mode shape [1,4–6]. By mathematical decomposition of the mode shape into pure bending and torsion mode shapes and of the aerodynamic work, it has also been shown that cross-coupling terms in the aerodynamic work, particularly the unsteady lift

* Bending in the sense that the blade sections vibrate perpendicular to the blade chord, i.e. perform a plunging motion in the blade-to-blade plane.

† Torsion in the sense that the blade twists along its half-chord axis, i.e. the blade sections oscillate in a pitching motion about half-chord.

from the twist motion acting on the bending motion, have a destabilizing effect. The unsteady lift created by the bending motion acting on the bending motion itself in contrast has a strong stabilizing effect [4,6]. However, most of these studies are limited to a single or a few selected inter-blade phase angles (IBPA) or nodal diameters, and/or few mode shapes, limiting the generality of the findings. Also, to the knowledge of the authors, no systematic experimental studies on the influence of mode shape on compressor flutter stability have been published.

The presented work is part of a joint experimental and numerical study on the effect of mode shape and reduced frequency on the flutter stability of a linear, subsonic compressor cascade, which was carried out at the Chair for Aero Engines at TU Berlin and the Rolls-Royce Vibration UTC at Imperial College London. Complementing a joint paper on the numerical investigation [7], this paper describes in more detail the experimental investigations and provides deeper insight into the stability trends based on an in-depth analysis of the AICs.

1.1. Test Case

FIGURE 1: BLADE SECTION MODE SHAPE DESCRIPTION

The test case is a combined plunge-pitch mode shape of a compressor blade section, which oscillates in a solid-body rotation about an axis at a distance x_F downstream from the leading edge (z_F from mid-chord), as depicted in Figure 1. The geometric relation between the *small* twist angle ϑ , torsion axis setback, and the LE, TE and plunge displacement amplitudes is:

$$\hat{\vartheta} \approx \sin(\hat{\vartheta}) = \frac{\hat{h}}{z_F} = \frac{\hat{h}_{LE} - \hat{h}_{TE}}{c} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{z_F}{c} = \frac{x_F}{c} - \frac{1}{2} = \frac{\hat{h}}{\hat{h}_{LE} - \hat{h}_{TE}} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{\hat{h}_{LE} + \hat{h}_{TE}}{\hat{h}_{LE} - \hat{h}_{TE}} \quad (2)$$

Based on a quasi-steady aerodynamic model for a single airfoil, the change in incidence due to pitch motion is identical to the twist displacement angle, while the incidence change due to plunge motion results from the superposition of plunge velocity and flow velocity [8]:

$$\theta_t(t) = \vartheta(t) = \hat{\vartheta} \cdot \sin(\omega t) \quad (3)$$

$$\theta_p(t) = \frac{-\dot{h}(t)}{U_0} = -\frac{\omega \cdot z_F \cdot \hat{\vartheta}}{U_0} \cos(\omega t) = -k \cdot \frac{z_F}{c} \hat{\vartheta} \cdot \cos(\omega t) \quad (4)$$

with $k = \omega \cdot c / U_0$ being the reduced frequency.

The minus sign in eq. (4) indicates that the momentary change in incidence creates an unsteady lift force in the opposite direction to the blade's momentary plunge velocity, providing a

fundamental explanation as to why, for attached flow, a plunging blade has a stabilizing effect on itself. With this in mind, the mode shape is characterized by the aeroelastic design parameter "plunge-to-twist incidence ratio" (PTIR):

$$\Phi_\theta = \frac{\hat{\theta}_p}{\hat{\theta}_t} = k \cdot \frac{z_F}{c} = k \cdot \left(\frac{x_F}{c} - \frac{1}{2} \right) \quad (5)$$

In the presented experimental study, a systematic variation of this incidence ratio parameter was conducted over a range of reduced frequencies.

1.2. Methodologies

Forced motion flutter testing in combination with an aerodynamic influence coefficient (AIC) method is employed. Harmonic motion in the designated mode shape is prescribed on the central blade of the cascade, and the unsteady pressure response on the vibrating blade and the stationary blades is observed to obtain the aerodynamic influence coefficients.

The flutter stability of the cascade is assessed by calculating the aerodynamic work per vibration cycle on the reference blade, which, for a solid body rotation about the torsion axis TA, is

$$W_{aero} = \int_0^T M_{TA}(t) \cdot \dot{\vartheta}(t) dt \quad (6)$$

where $\dot{\vartheta}(t)$ is the time derivative of the angular displacement (i.e. the modal velocity) and $M_{TA}(t)$ is the aerodynamic moment about the torsion axis (i.e., the modal force). For a purely harmonic blade oscillation, it can be shown that the aerodynamic work depends only on the magnitudes of the modal displacement and the 1st harmonic of the modal force, and on the phase angle of the modal force with respect to the displacement, φ_1 .

$$W_{aero} = \pi \cdot \hat{\vartheta} \cdot \hat{M}_{TA,1} \cdot \sin(\varphi_1) \quad (7)$$

Without mechanical damping, the stability of the blade depends only on the sign of φ_1 . For $\varphi_1 > 0$, i.e., if the modal force is leading the displacement, the aerodynamic work is positive and the vibration is excited. For $\varphi_1 < 0$, the vibration is damped.

The modal force can be normalized by $q \cdot bc^2 \cdot \hat{\vartheta} \cdot x_F / c$ to define dimensionless complex modal force coefficients:

$$\tilde{c}_M = \hat{c}_M \cdot e^{i\varphi} = \frac{\hat{M}_{TA}}{q \cdot bc^2 \cdot \hat{\vartheta} \cdot x_F / c} \cdot e^{i\varphi} \quad (8)$$

Assuming linearity of the unsteady aerodynamics, the modal force in a travelling wave mode with inter-blade phase angle σ can be expressed as a Fourier series of the AICs:

$$\tilde{c}_M^\sigma = \sum_{m=-N/2}^{+N/2} \tilde{c}_{M_{aic}}^{m,0} \cdot e^{-i\sigma \cdot m} \quad (9)$$

Here, \tilde{c}_M^σ is the modal force coefficient for reference blade 0 in a travelling wave mode, and $\tilde{c}_{M_{aic}}^{m,0}$ are the aerodynamic influence coefficients for the modal force induced by blade m on blade 0.

Following the recommendations by [9], the dimensionless damping parameter Ξ is defined as:

$$\Xi = \frac{-W_{aero}}{\pi \cdot q \cdot bc^2 \cdot (\hat{h}_{LE}/c)^2} = -\frac{\Im(\tilde{c}_M)}{x_F/c} \quad (10)$$

2. EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

2.1. Flutter Test Rig

- 1) Holes for stagnation temperature and pressure measurements
- 2) Static pressure holes for nozzle pressure gradient
- 3) Pitot probe for inlet dynamic pressure (\rightarrow inlet flow velocity)
- 4) Oscillating air foil compressor cascade, unsteady blade surface pressure measurements

FIGURE 2: FLUTTER TEST WIND TUNNEL

The experimental investigation was done on a linear cascade with 11 blades in an open-return low-speed wind tunnel. The rectangular measurement section housing the cascade is 955 mm tall (equivalent to 12 blade passage heights) and 200 mm wide. Blade span is 197 mm, leaving 1.5 mm tip gap on either side. The cascade geometry is summarized in Figure 3.

FIGURE 3: CASCADE GEOMETRY AND NOMENCLATURE

The cascade front has a fixed 45° angle to the inlet flow direction (i.e., the inlet flow angle β w. r. t. the “machine axis” is fixed at 45°). The blades are mounted to the back wall of the measurement section at half-chord and can be rotated to change the mean angle of attack α_0 . In doing so, the mean stagger angle γ_0 is also changed according to $\gamma_0 = \beta - \alpha_0$. For the aeroelastic experiments, $\alpha_0 = 2^\circ$ ($\gamma_0 = 43^\circ$) was used (cf. section 4.1).

The blade section is a slightly modified version of Standard Configuration 1, which was adopted from previous experimental investigations at DLR [10] and TU Berlin [11,12]. It features a NACA65-series thickness distribution with 6% maximum thickness (modified for finite thickness at the trailing edge) over a circular arc mean camber line with approx. 6° camber angle.

All blades in the cascade are equipped with transition strips on the suction surface at 17% chord to prevent flow separation.

The highest achievable flow velocity in the measurement section is around 38 m/s, during the experiments, $U_0 = 30$ m/s

was used. The corresponding Reynolds and Mach numbers are $Re_c \approx 285\,000$ and $Ma \approx 0.085$, depending on the temperature, and the inlet turbulence intensity is $u'/U_0 \approx 0.2\%$. A detailed account of the base flow properties is given in [12].

2.2. Vibrating Blade Module (VBM)

For implementation of the variable combined mode shape (as depicted in Figure 1) in the wind tunnel, a lever with a long slot, together with a mechanical drive system, is mounted to a traversing plate, which is connected to the outside of the wind tunnel side wall by linear bearings. This unit can be moved parallel to the flow to change the lever axis location relative to the vibrating blade (z_F). Through an aperture in the wind tunnel wall, the vibrating blade is mounted to a sliding block in the slot, which can be unclamped, so the lever can be moved while the blade maintains its position in the cascade, temporarily fixed with a dowel pin. The drive system consists of an electric step motor with an eccentric attached to its shaft, a scotch yoke, which perfectly converts the rotational to sinusoidal linear motion, and a connecting rod, which transfers this motion to the tip of the lever, creating a constant angular displacement and hence twist incidence amplitude of $\hat{\vartheta} = 1.5^\circ$. A digital laser triangulation distance sensor (Micro-Epsilon ILD1420) is used to track the displacement at the lever holding the vibrating blade, providing a reference for the phase of the unsteady pressures.

FIGURE 4: VIBRATING BLADE MODULE (VBM) AND BLADES

TABLE 1: VBM DESIGN OPERATING POINTS

Reduced frequency	$k = \{0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6\}$
PTIR	$\Phi_\theta = \{0.16, 0.2, 0.25, 0.3, 0.35, 0.4\}$
Lever length	$z_F = 40 \dots 200$ mm
Torsion axis setback	$x_F/c = 0.7667 \dots 1.833$
Vibration frequency	$f = \{6.4, 9.6, 12.7, 15.9, 19.1\}$ Hz
Vibration amplitude	$\hat{\vartheta} = 1.5^\circ = 0.0262$ rad

The aerodynamic and inertial forces acting on the oscillating blade exert a torque about the longitudinal axis of the lever, thus

torsional stiffness was a primary target for the mechanical design of the lever and its pivot axis, in order to minimize undesired flap motion of the blade. At the same time, the lever needs to be light weight to avoid excessive motor loads. To achieve this, the lever was designed as a half-open structure with strengthening ribs oriented at $\pm 45^\circ$, and the pivot axis is supported by a bridge.

VBM Validation

To assess the fidelity of the mechanical mode shape implementation, experimental modal analysis (impact hammer testing) and measurements of the elastic deformation due to inertial forces of the blade-lever assembly were performed.

For the modal analysis, the measurement blade was installed in a fixed blade mount as well as in the VBM lever in the position furthest away from the axis. The Eigenmodes with the lowest frequencies are first flap and first torsion. In both modes, the deformation occurs mostly in and around the blade root piece, while the carbon fiber shell remains mostly flat. The modal frequencies are summarized in Table 2. The lowest modal frequency of the measurement blade in the lever (1F) is more than three times greater than the highest oscillation frequency in the experiments, hence unwanted resonance can be ruled out.

TABLE 2: MEASUREMENT BLADE EIGENFREQUENCIES

	Flap mode (1F)	Torsion mode (1T)
Fixed blade mount	80.9 Hz	162.3 Hz
Blade in lever	67.5 Hz	136.8 Hz

FIGURE 5: VIBRATING BLADE DEFORMATION TEST SCHEMATIC

To measure the elastic blade deformation due to inertial forces, the periodic displacement was measured on a nine-point grid on the vibrating blade PS, using the ILD1420 sensor, as schematically depicted in Figure 5. All operating points of the VBM for the aeroelastic experiments were tested this way at operational frequency and at 1 Hz for reference. It was found that the shell of the blade deflects in the form of a rigid body, which, in addition to the desired parallel rotation about the lever pivot axis performs a flap motion about the lever longitudinal axis and some twist motion about its half-chord axis. Consequently, the

true plunge-to-twist incidence ratio, defined in terms of LE and TE displacements as $\Phi_\theta = \frac{k}{2} \cdot \frac{H_{LE} + H_{LE}}{H_{LE} - H_{LE}}$, is generally larger than the design value and increasing with span-wise distance from the blade root, as well as with vibration frequency. The excess plunge-to-twist ratio was found to be less than 4% for $k = 0.6$ ($f = 19.1\text{Hz}$) at the outer end of the pressure tap zone.

FIGURE 6: EXCESS DISPLACEMENT AMPLITUDE DUE TO INERTIAL FORCES

TABLE 3: MEASURED VS. DESIGN INCIDENCE RATIO

$\Phi(H_{LE}, H_{TE})$	Design incidence ratio					
	$\Phi = 0.16$	$\Phi = 0.2$	$\Phi = 0.25$	$\Phi = 0.3$	$\Phi = 0.35$	$\Phi = 0.4$
$k = 0.2$	0,160	0,200	0,251			
$k = 0.3$	0,161	0,201	0,251	0,301	0,352	0,403
$k = 0.4$	0,162	0,203	0,254	0,304	0,353	0,404
$k = 0.5$	0,164	0,205	0,255	0,307	0,357	0,408
$k = 0.6$	0,166	0,208	0,259	0,310	0,361	0,412

Because of the staggered alignment of the pressure taps, each pressure tap experiences a slightly different true mode shape, so that it isn't possible to exactly specify the true incidence ratio of an aeroelastic measurement or apply a correction factor. This mode shape error was therefore left unaccounted in the evaluation of the aeroelastic measurement campaigns.

2.3. Pressure Measurement System

For blade surface pressure measurements, two of the blades are equipped with 20 pressure taps each (10 SS, 10 PS). The taps are staggered in the spanwise direction and bunched towards the leading edge of the blade. A set of 20 piezo-resistive differential pressure transducers (Endevco 8510B-1), placed outside the wind tunnel, were connected to one measurement blade at a time through metal pipes inside the blades and silicone tubes outside.

Tap holes, internal pipes and silicone tubes have a nominal inner diameter of 0.5mm. All tubes have a length of 40 cm, while the internal pipes have individual lengths between 10 and 17 cm.

FIGURE 7: MEASUREMENT BLADE

The transducers have a range of $\pm 1PSI$ gauge ($\pm 7kPa$). To allow accurate reading of the much smaller steady and unsteady blade surface pressures, they were calibrated against precision pressure cells with 25 Pa, 100 Pa and 1000 Pa ranges. The transducers exhibit linear behaviour within the $\pm 1kPa$ range, as shown in Figure 8 and Figure 9.

FIGURE 8: PRESSURE TRANSDUCER CALIBRATION POINTS

FIGURE 9: PRESSURE TRANSDUCER LINEARIZATION ERROR

Dynamic transfer functions of the pressure lines were calibrated on-site in a pressure chamber (Figure 10), exposing either the PS or SS pressure taps to a sinusoidal pressure oscillation of $\pm 200Pa$ with adjustable frequency (1-30 Hz) and comparing the readings on the recessed mounted transducers to a reference transducer on the chamber side wall. Complex transfer functions accounting for amplitude attenuation and phase lag in the pressure lines are obtained by comparing the 1st harmonic Fourier coefficients. The calibrated transfer functions for one of the measurement blades are shown in Figure 11.

$$F_i(f) = \frac{p_i^{1H}(f)}{p_{ref}^{1H}(f)} \quad (11)$$

FIGURE 10: PRESSURE LINE CALIBRATION DEVICE

FIGURE 11: TRANSFER FUNCTIONS OF PRESSURE LINES

2.4. Data Acquisition, Processing and Evaluation

A DEWETRON data acquisition system was employed for synchronized recording of the 20 blade surface pressure transducers, the displacement sensor and sensors to monitor inlet flow conditions. 7.5 kHz sampling rate and a 3 kHz Butterworth low-pass filter were used. For each aeroelastic measurement, roughly 1800 oscillation periods were recorded. To separate the aerodynamic response to the blade vibration from flow turbulence and other noise, the unsteady pressure measurement data was evaluated in the frequency domain. The following steps were taken in data evaluation:

- Determine oscillation period lengths and starting times based on the noise-free displacement sensor signal, crop signals to integer number of oscillation periods to minimize frequency spread in the discrete Fourier transform (DFT).
- DFT of the cropped displacement and pressure signals, pick complex Fourier coefficients $\hat{\delta}^{1H}$ and \hat{p}^{1H} corresponding to blade oscillation frequency f_{osc} .
- Compensate output delay (3 cycles) of the digital laser sensor on displacement 1st harmonic, normalize to unit magnitude.
- Divide pressure signal 1st harmonic by line transfer function to compensate phase lag and amplitude attenuation, convert transducer voltage to pressure.
- Divide \hat{p}^{1H} by $\hat{\delta}^{1H}$ to get the unsteady pressure phase angle relative to the displacement.

The 1st harmonic of the pressure is then normalized by dynamic pressure q and the dimensionless leading edge displacement amplitude to form the unsteady pressure coefficient:

$$\tilde{c}_p = \frac{\hat{p}^{1H}}{p_{dyn} \cdot \hat{\delta} \cdot x_F/c} = \frac{\hat{p}^{1H}}{p_{dyn} \cdot \hat{h}_{LE}/c} \quad (12)$$

The modal force coefficients are calculated by integrating the unsteady pressure force, multiplied by the local distance from the torsion axis, over the blade surface.

$$\tilde{c}_M = \int_{LE}^{TE} (\tilde{c}_{p,SS}(x) - \tilde{c}_{p,PS}(x)) \cdot \frac{(x - x_F)}{c^2} \cdot dx \quad (13)$$

Figure 12 depicts amplitude spectra of the pressure signals. It shows that the first and second harmonic of the pressure response to the blade oscillation (markers) are very clearly identified, despite the turbulent background noise. Two other sharp peaks at first and second engine order of the wind tunnel's radial blower are also visible.

FIGURE 12: PRESSURE TRANSDUCER AMPLITUDE SPECTRA

3. CFD SIMULATION SETUP

To complement the experiments and gain an understanding of the aerodynamics of the finite cascade, 2D CFD simulations of the base flow (RANS) and of the aeroelastic experiments (URANS) were done with ANSYS CFX v19.2, using the $k-\omega$ SST turbulence model (fully turbulent, no transition modelling). The computational domain is a mid-span section of the wind tunnels measurement section. The block-structured mesh is one element thick and uses approximately 3.4×10^5 elements. Average first element y^+ on the blades is ≈ 0.7 , maximum y^+ (at the LE) < 10 . Automatic wall functions were used.

At the outlet, an area-averaged static pressure of $0Pa$, and at the inlet a constant total pressure of $533.15Pa$ (both relative to a reference pressure of 1 bar) were prescribed, so that the mass flow averaged inlet velocity was $30 m/s$. Inlet total temperature was $298.15K$ and turbulence intensity 1%.

For aeroelastic simulations, 22 vibration cycles were simulated, each resolved with 50 time steps.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Base Flow Aerodynamics

The CFD simulations reveal a strong effect of the top and bottom walls on the pressure and velocity field around the cascade at non-zero angles of attack. Because the straight walls prevent the cascade from deflecting the flow as it naturally would, they impose a pressure gradient between both ends of the cascade, which increases with AoA, as seen in Figure 13 for $\alpha_0 = 2^\circ$.

FIGURE 13: STATIC PRESSURE FIELD IN THE MEASUREMENT SECTION ($U_0 = 30$ m/s, $\alpha_0 = 2^\circ$)

Accordingly, with increasing α_0 the blade loading becomes more non-uniform, with the highest loading next to the walls and the smallest loading on blade -2, as depicted in Figure 14. It is also noteworthy that for positive AoA, the blade loading in the finite cascade is substantially higher than in an infinite cascade, whereas for 0° AoA, where the net blade loading is very small (and in fact slightly negative due to cascading effects, despite the positive camber), the blade loadings are very similar.

FIGURE 14: STEADY BLADE SURFACE c_p DISTRIBUTIONS AT 0, 2, 4° AOA, CYCLIC VS LINEAR CASCADE (CFD)

Time-averaged blade pressure measurements in the experimental cascade at 0 and 2° AoA without blade motion are in good agreement with the CFD results. The measurements confirm the CFD predictions regarding the non-uniform blade loading and

the pressure gradient along the cascade (visible in the decline in TE pressure from blade to blade). Compared to the simulations, the measured c_p profiles are offset to higher values. This is due to pressure losses on the wind tunnel side walls $\Delta p_{loss, TE \rightarrow Outlet}$, which aren't captured in the 2D CFD, in combination with the definition $c_p = \frac{p - p_{amb}}{q}$.

FIGURE 15: MEASURED VS SIMULATED c_p DISTRIBUTIONS

4.2. Unsteady Pressures, AICs and Cascade Stability

Unsteady blade surface pressure distributions from CFD and measurements are in very close agreement (Figure 16). In terms of the shapes, the results found here also resemble those presented by [13].

On the central (vibrating) blade 0, the unsteady pressure amplitudes on the pressure and suction surface are almost identical, but the phases are offset by almost exactly 180° over most of the blade chord. The unsteady pressure difference between the surfaces, which creates the unsteady lift and moment about the torsion axis, is therefore almost twice as large as the unsteady pressure amplitude on either surface. Most of the unsteady lift/moment is generated near the leading edge, within the first 10-15% chord, as reported by [14]. Remarkably, the phase distributions on both surfaces of blade 0 are sloped upwards, meaning that the change in unsteady pressure occurs first at the trailing edge and is then propagated upstream towards the leading edge. This phenomenon has also been pointed out in [14]. The slope in the phase distribution is more pronounced at higher reduced frequencies.

On the suction side neighbours of the vibrating blade (blades -1 and -2), the unsteady pressure amplitudes are also largest near the leading edge, however, the amplitudes are notably larger on the pressure surface which is facing the vibrating blade. Accordingly, the pressure fluctuations on the pressure surfaces of blades -1 and -2 are in sync with the suction surface of blade 0. On blade +1, the immediate pressure side neighbour of the vibrating blade, the largest unsteady pressure amplitudes occur on the aft portion of the suction side, which creates a flow passage with the pressure surface of blade 0.

Unsteady c_p Distributions (Exp. vs CFX); $k = 0.3$; $\Phi = 0.3$

Unsteady c_p Distributions (Exp. vs CFX); $k = 0.6$; $\Phi = 0.3$

FIGURE 16a: UNSTEADY c_p DISTRIBUTIONS ($k = 0.3$)

16b: UNSTEADY c_p DISTRIBUTIONS ($k = 0.6$)

Figure 17 gives an overview over the AICs at different incidence ratios and reduced frequencies in terms of relative magnitude and phase angle (with respect to the displacement). Narrow bars with solid filling represent measurements, wide bars with transparent filling CFD. The AIC magnitudes are normalized by the blade 0 AIC for each case, to eliminate the effect of the somewhat arbitrary modal force normalization and

instead highlight the neighbour blades' potential for destabilizing the reference blade. The relative magnitude of the blade 0 AIC is unity for all cases by definition, so the ordinate axis limit is set to 0.5 to provide a better resolution of the other AICs. As with the unsteady pressure distributions, measurement and CFD match very well and show consistent trends in the AICs with regard to incidence ratio and frequency parameters.

FIGURE 17a: RELATIVE AIC MAGNITUDE (EXP. VS CFX)

○ As incidence ratio is increased, the phase angle of all AICs is reduced. The change in phase with PTIR is not equal for all AICs: the phases of blades -1 and -2 change more than others.

○ Relative AIC magnitudes change very little with incidence ratio, except for blade -1, whose relative influence increases with PTIR. Considering Figure 16, we assume that this is because the influence of a vibrating blade on its next pressure side neighbour results mostly from pressure fluctuations on the

17b: AIC PHASE (EXP. VS CFX)

aft portion of the suction surface, which are more sensitive to plunge motion, whereas all other AICs are dominated by pressure fluctuations near the leading edge, which are more dependent on effective incidence change, regardless of whether this incidence results from plunge or pitch motion.

○ As reduced frequency is increased (at const. Φ_θ), the phase of the blade 0 AIC remains almost constant, but the phase of other blades (especially ± 2 and ± 3) is reduced. Also, the

relative magnitudes of the ± 2 and ± 3 AICs is decreased. We conclude that at higher reduced frequencies, the unsteady pressure propagation from the vibrating blade to further away blades is damped and delayed.

FIGURE 18: MODAL FORCE COEFFICIENTS – AICS AND TWM SYNTHESIS – EFFECT OF INCIDENCE RATIO (PTIR)

FIGURE 19: MODAL FORCE COEFFICIENTS – AICS AND TWM SYNTHESIS – EFFECT OF REDUCED FREQUENCY

The significance of these trends for cascade stability becomes apparent in Figure 18 and 19, where phasors for the AICs and the locus curves of the TWM modal force coefficients are plotted in the complex plane. As incidence ratio is increased, phasors for all blades are rotated clockwise. Consequently, the imaginary part of $\tilde{c}_{M_{aic}}^0$, which contributes the stabilizing effect of the vibrating blade on itself, is increased, and the TWM locus curve, which is obtained by revolving the other AICs around the tip of $\tilde{c}_{M_{aic}}^0$ according to eq. (9), is gradually moved out of the unstable zone. Note that the shape and size (relative to $\tilde{c}_{M_{aic}}^0$) of the TWM locus curve remain relatively constant (Figure 18).

In contrast, as reduced frequency is increased while keeping Φ_θ constant, the phase angle of $\tilde{c}_{M_{aic}}^0$ and with it the

stabilizing effect of blade 0 on itself remain nearly constant, however, a reduced destabilizing contribution from the other blade pairs, especially ± 2 and ± 3 , flattens the shape of the TWM locus curve and improves cascade stability (Figure 19). This is partly due to the decreased relative AIC magnitudes of these blades, but also (less apparent, but equally important) due to their relative phase angles.

These stability trends are also visible in the damping curves in Figure 20.

FIGURE 20: AERO-DAMPING VS IBPA (EXP. VS CFX)

The flutter stability of the cascade is summarized in a stability map, which shows a contour of minimum aerodamping (at any IBPA) in the reduced frequency (k) versus torsion axis setback (x_F/c) space, based on CFD simulations. The damping is minimal and negative in the bottom left corner and increases monotonically with k and x_F/c . The stability limit, defined by zero aerodamping, is marked for TWM synthesis from 7 and 11 AICs (CFD) and 7 experimentally obtained AICs. For reduced frequencies above 0.4, the stability limits are well approximated by lines of constant PTIR, but for lower k , the limits shift to increasingly larger PTIR, presumably due to the greater destabilizing effect of further away blade pairs.

The stability limits for 7 and 11 AICs from CFD are almost identical, indicating good convergence of the AIC method. We see that the experimental cascade is slightly less stable than the CFD, which can be explained by the slightly less negative phase of the blade 0 AIC and the consistently smaller relative magnitude of the blade -1 AIC (since it is out of phase with blade +1 in the IBPA-domain, this AIC reduces the destabilizing contribution of the ± 1 pair).

FIGURE 21: CASCADE STABILITY MAP

4.3. Summary of Findings

The influence of the vibrating blade on itself is always stabilizing, while other blades (mainly the first pressure side neighbour) vibrating at forward-travelling, low nodal diameter IPBAs, can destabilize the reference blade. As PTIR is increased, the phase of the complex modal force coefficients (AICs) of all blades is decreased, increasing the stabilizing effect of the vibrating blade on itself and overall cascade stability.

Within the considered parameter range, the impact of reduced frequency is eliminated to a large extent if the incidence ratio is kept constant, requiring the torsion axis setback to be adjusted accordingly. However, second order effects of k are apparent, predominantly at the lower end of the frequency range, and on the 2nd and 3rd neighbours of the reference blade.

The flutter stability limit for the cascade was found near an incidence ratio of ≈ 0.3 , much lower than the hypothesized value of 1.0, which was based on empirical findings for aero engine fans. It is assumed that this discrepancy is due to vastly different flow conditions and the absence of 3D-flow and acoustic effects in the present test case. This calls for the inclusion of additional flow parameters such as Mach number, aerodynamic loading, blade geometry and stagger angle, which are being addressed in an ongoing follow-up research project.

5. CONCLUSION

The results presented in this work underline the significance of PTIR as an aeroelastic design parameter that should be considered early in the aero-mechanical design process to ensure flutter-free blade design. While it is, by itself, not sufficient to accurately predict the stability limit of a given blade design, it provides a physical understanding of the global flutter stability trends of combined 1F mode shapes, which can be exploited. The results confirm previous findings from other researchers that aeroelastic stability of flap mode shapes can be improved by increasing the frequency parameter and/or by reducing the twist component (increasing the plunge component) of the mode shape. More importantly, the results of this research indicate that it is even feasible to improve flutter stability by sacrificing blade stiffness (reduced frequency) in order to increase the plunge component of the mode shape, on the condition that this increases the plunge-to-twist incidence ratio.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Peng C., and Vahdati M., 2002, "The Effects of Fundamental Mode Shapes on Flutter Stability of an Aero Engine Axial Compressor Blades: Introduction of a Modified Reduced Frequency Parameter," 7th National Turbine Engine High Cycle fatigue (HCF) Conference: Palm Beach Gardens, Florida, USA / 14-17 May 2002.
- [2] Panovsky J., and Kielb R. E., 2000, "A Design Method to Prevent Low Pressure Turbine Blade Flutter," J. Eng. Gas Turbines Power, **122**(1), p. 89.
- [3] Nowinski M., and Panovsky J., 2000, "Flutter Mechanisms in Low Pressure Turbine Blades," Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power, **122**(1), pp. 82–88.
- [4] Zhao F., 2018, "Impact of Mode Shape and Acoustic Gust on Blade Flutter Stability," Proceedings of the International Symposium on Unsteady Aerodynamics, Aeroacoustics & Aeroelasticity of Turbomachines, **2018**.

- [5] Nipkau J., Power B., and Jordan M., 2017, "Aeromechanical Design and Test of a Modern Highly Loaded Fan," *Volume 2B: Turbomachinery*, American Society of Mechanical Engineers.
- [6] Vahdati M., and Cumpsty N., 2016, "Aeroelastic Instability in Transonic Fans," *J. Eng. Gas Turbines Power*, **138**(2), p. 22604.
- [7] Hill G., Gambel J., Schneider S., Peitsch D., and Stapelfeldt S., 2022, "Aeroelastic Stability of Combined Plunge-Pitch Mode Shapes in a Linear Compressor Cascade," *IJTPP*, **7**(1), p. 7.
- [8] Cumpsty N. A., 2004. *Compressor aerodynamics*, Krieger, Malabar, Fla.
- [9] Böles A., and Fransson T. H., Eds., 1986. *Aeroelasticity in Turbomachines Comparison of Theoretical and Experimental Cascade Results + Appendix A5 All Experimental and Theoretical Results for the 9 Standard Configurations*.
- [10] Hennings H., and Send W., 1998, "Experimental Investigation and Theoretical Prediction of Flutter Behavior of

a Plane Cascade in Low Speed Flow," *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, **120**(4), pp. 766–774.

- [11] Malzacher L., Schwarze C., Motta V., and Peitsch D., 2019, "Experimental Investigation of an Aerodynamically Mistuned Oscillating Compressor Cascade," *J. Turbomach*, **141**(7).
- [12] Malzacher L., Geist S., Motta V., Peitsch D., and Hennings H., 2019, "A Low-Speed Compressor Test Rig for Flutter Investigations," *Journal of Turbomachinery*, **141**(5).
- [13] Buffum D. H., and Fleeter S., 1990, "Oscillating Cascade Aerodynamics by an Experimental Influence Coefficient Technique," *Journal of Propulsion and Power*, **6**(5), pp. 612–620.
- [14] Carta F. O., and St. Hilaire A. O., 1978, "Experimentally Determined Stability Parameters of a Subsonic Cascade Oscillating Near Stall," *Journal of Engineering for Power*, **100**(1), pp. 111–120.

In other words, only the 1st harmonic contributes to the aerodynamic work, while the static mean and higher harmonics have no effect.

Combining equations (A1), (A3), (A4) and (A5) gives:

$$W_{aero} = \pi \cdot \hat{\vartheta} \cdot \hat{M}_{TA,1} \cdot \sin(\varphi_1) \quad (A6)$$

APPENDIX

A1. CALCULATION OF AERODYNAMIC WORK

The flutter stability of the cascade is assessed by calculating the aerodynamic work per vibration cycle on the reference blade, which, for a solid body rotation about the torsion axis TA, is

$$W_{aero} = \int_0^T M_{TA}(t) \cdot \dot{\vartheta}(t) dt \quad (A1)$$

where $\dot{\vartheta}(t)$ is the time derivative of the angular displacement (i.e. the modal velocity) and $M_{TA}(t)$ is the aerodynamic moment about the torsion axis (i.e., the modal force). The latter can be expressed in terms of the moment about half-chord, the lift force perpendicular to the chord and the distance between half-chord and torsion axis. For the two-dimensional blade section, the force and moments are considered *per unit span*.

$$M_{TA}(t) = M_{HC}(t) + z_F \cdot L_P(t) \quad (A2)$$

For a purely sinusoidal displacement $\vartheta(t) = \hat{\vartheta} \cdot \sin(\omega t)$, the modal velocity is:

$$\dot{\vartheta}(t) = \omega \cdot \hat{\vartheta} \cdot \cos(\omega t) \quad (A3)$$

Assuming the modal force is periodic, it can be expressed as a Fourier series:

$$M_{TA}(t) = \bar{M}_{TA} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \hat{M}_{TA,n} \cdot \sin(n\omega t + \varphi_n) \quad (A4)$$

where \bar{M}_{TA} is the static mean and $\hat{M}_{TA,n}$ and φ_n are amplitudes and phase angles (with respect to the modal displacement) of the n^{th} harmonic. It can be shown that:

$$\int_0^T \omega \cdot \cos(\omega t) \cdot \sin(n\omega t + \varphi_n) dt = \begin{cases} \pi \sin \varphi_n, & n \in \mathbb{N}_0 = 1 \\ 0, & n \in \mathbb{N}_0 \neq 1 \end{cases} \quad (A5)$$

A2. NORMALIZATION OF MODAL FORCES, AERODYNAMIC WORK AND DAMPING

The modal force is normalized by $q \cdot bc^2 \cdot \hat{\vartheta} \cdot x_F/c$ to define dimensionless complex modal force coefficients:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{c}_M &= \hat{c}_M \cdot e^{i\varphi} = \frac{\hat{M}_{TA}}{q \cdot bc^2 \cdot \hat{\vartheta} \cdot x_F/c} \cdot e^{i\varphi} \\ &= \frac{\hat{M}_{TA}}{q \cdot bc^2 \cdot \hat{h}_{LE}/c} \cdot e^{i\varphi} \end{aligned} \quad (A7)$$

Combining (A6) and (A7), the dimensional aerodynamic work per cycle, expressed in terms of the complex modal force coefficient is:

$$\begin{aligned} W_{aero} &= \pi \cdot q \cdot bc^2 \cdot \hat{\vartheta}^2 \cdot \frac{x_F}{c} \cdot \hat{c}_M \cdot \sin(\varphi_1) \\ &= \pi \cdot q \cdot bc^2 \cdot \left(\frac{\hat{h}_{LE}}{c}\right)^2 \cdot \frac{\Im(\tilde{c}_M)}{x_F/c} \end{aligned} \quad (A8)$$

It is then normalized by $-\pi \cdot q \cdot bc^2 \cdot (\hat{h}_{LE}/c)^2$ to define the dimensionless damping parameter Ξ :

$$\Xi = \frac{-W_{aero}}{\pi \cdot q \cdot bc^2 \cdot (\hat{h}_{LE}/c)^2} = -\frac{\Im(\tilde{c}_M)}{x_F/c} \quad (A9)$$